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RESPONSE PAPER

LAST NAME: Halane

FIRST NAME: Hassan

PROGRAM CODE: DILT

COURSE CODE: ACA-401D

PERIOD NUMBER: 1

INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma

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Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied U.S. U.K. conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.
The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)
The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references
The author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)
The author used the following software: Microsoft Word 365 on Windows 10

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Meaning and steps of essay writing (EUCLID 2021, 1-4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 5-6)
3. Taking the writer's views seriously (EUCLID 2021, 15-15)
4. Turabian style of writing (EUCLID 2021, 24-26)
5. Plain English language (EUCLID 2021, 42-56)
6. British English (EUCLID 2019, 27-34)
7. Latin abbreviations (EUCLID 2019, 56-59)

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1) INTRODUCTION

ACA-401D period one EUCLID course is dedicated to academic writing to enhance, alleviate, and improve students' academic skills at Euclid University. Although I practice writing in my daily work activities and assignments, I must admit that this course adds value to my career advancement, particularly to my academic writing. The system guides me through the step-by-step educational writing process and makes me familiar and complaint with EUCLID required of writing academic papers. The study has properly addressed many questions lingering in mind since I was at school, such as using the personal pronoun in academic writing. In this short response paper, I will discuss seven key concepts (points) based on the study of the course materials. The seven concepts that I am going to explain are: 1) Meaning and steps of essay writing; 2) Plagiarism; 3) Taking the writer's views seriously; 4) Turabian style of writing; 5) Plain English language; 6) British English, and 7) Latin abbreviations.

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2) MEANING AND STEPS OF ESSAY WRITING.

The first question is what essay writing is? I find asking this question is relevant as the EUCLID coursepack did not provide a proper definition of essay writing. The first chapter of the ACA-401D period one (1) coursepack (EUCLID 2021) rightly covers the process and steps of essay writing. It could be defined through academic writing as one of the main components and starting -up of academic writing. Therefore, in General, academic writing

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is typical writing used in high school and college classes (Oshima, Alice, and Hogue 2007, 3). I guess the definition of the terms is needed. However, the challenge is not about defining essay or academic writing but doing it systematically and correctly. To me, good scholarly writing means future academic success.

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Becoming a professional academic writer is an excellent career and worth rewording in any given assignment or function. However, academic writing is "not a linear process" and is straightforward (EUCLID 2021, 1). People need to practice it and grow in it slowly until they reach the required milestone. So much so, I believe achieving such a milestone requires a lot of effort and time to learn and excel in how you pursue is good academic writing.

The EUCLID coursepack(EUCLID 2021, 1, 2, 3, 4) illustrated six steps of the academic writing process for that purpose.¹ The six (6) steps listed below presents a clear road map for academic writing progress. I find them interesting, and I will adopt them in all my writings, not only for this paper but also for the subsequent papers and throughout my entire period of study at EUCLID.

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3) PLAGIARISM

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There is no doubt that plagiarism is severe misconduct, and it is also the best-known example among other academic misbehaviors. Academic institutions define Plagiarism in their rules and regulations or their manuals to guide their staff and students while engaging in academic writing. As a result, the EULID University as a higher learning institution provided such guidance as well. For example, the second chapter of the ACA-401D period one (1) coursepack defined Plagiarism broadly, and I quote," Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information" (EUCLID 2021,5).

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Meaning plagiarism is claiming someone's work without a proper citation and acknowledgment. I agree with the definition mentioned above, but I would like to comment on the term "information" mentioned in the definition. In this context, I would prefer to use the term "work" instead of "information." I see the word "work" is a more general, and it includes information, innovation, and any other personal efforts and skills.

Furthermore, the dentition also mentions that authors must get credit for their effort to avoid Plagiarism. However, mastering how to acknowledge the source is also equally important, if not more. Writers might involve plagiarism without being fully aware of what requires or does not require citation for their academic writing. To emphasize more, the writers are guilt of plagiarism if they do not follow respective plagiarism guidelines by the individual institutions. For that reason, It is clear to me now that Plagiarism is a serious

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¹ The six steps of the academic writing process adopted by Euclid University are, starting, researching, organizing, writing, referencing, and lastly, editing.

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business in the academic world. The only way I can detect it is to comply with the University's educational guidelines and seek advice from my supervisors and instructors.

4) TAKING THE WRITER'S VIEWS SERIOUSLY

There are professional rules of thumb in academic writings that authors must follow and respect during their paper writings. To know more about the term, the second chapter of the ACA-401D period one (1) coursepack (EUCLID 2021) summarized some of them for students' guidance and assistance. As I studied, I found them very helpful in the academic sphere of writing. But one of the rules of thumb attracted me, and I am so closely connected to it since I learned it from the coursepack material. That is, "Take the views you are discussing seriously" (EUCLID 2021, 15). To examine other scholarly views carefully and honestly is relevant and timely advice that I must consider during my writings. The statement indicates that there is a great deal of divergence of opinions among academic writers. In other words, all writers cannot belong to the same school of thought when it comes to intellectual deliberation and contestation. It is also for the academic interest and development to have a different point of view towards an issue.

In addition, the coursepack material provided a technique to warrant the implementation of the rule, which is to argue against me "argue against yourself" (EUCLID 2021, 15). To test the validity of your conclusion concerning someone's else viewpoint, you must have clear evidence to support your decision. That means you criticize your testimony against yourself, which can lead you to qualify or disqualify your argument.

From now onwards, I am committed to carefully evaluating the author's Point of view before judging them to avoid misinterpretation and misrepresentation of their ideas and concepts.

5) TURABIAN STYLE OF WRITING

I support the idea of choosing a specific style of writing or formatting before starting an essay. There are several styles of formatting that institutions or publication houses use to guide and assist writers and publishers. Turabian style of writing is one of them. For instance, the EUCLID coursepack (EUCLID 2021, 24) instructs the students to follow and apply Turabian writing style. It is a straightforward style for high and University students writing academic papers, theses, and dissertations that are not for publication. I fully comprehend why EUCLID sticks with one type of writing to unify the University's version of academic paper's writing and facilitate and create one single authoritative style that reviewers and writers can quickly work with each other.

My assessment towards adopting the Turabian style of writing as an appropriate style is positive because it is simple and easy to follow compared to other academic styles. After all, it is an Author-date style of version (www.chicagomanualofstyle.org). It is an in-text citation that requires me to insert a few pieces of information with no compulsory footnote.

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6) PLAIN ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Using reader-friendly and straightforward writing is recommended, and it is getting more attention in academic papers. The most important thing for writing is to make the reader understand the message comprehensively and clearly. The primary responsibility lies with the writers to know the target audience and to make sure their writing is understood.

In general, it is not easy to communicate in plain language regardless of our language. My concern is about using in simple English language since it is not my mother tongue. The question is, what does plain English language mean? It is because not every writer is familiar with the notion of the Plain English language. The Plain Writing Act of 2010 defines it as follows; -"Writing that is clear, concise, well-organized, and follows other best practices appropriate to the subject or field and intended audience" (www.plainlanguage.gov). The EUCLID course pack also defines the plain English language whereby the writer should use short sentences with phrases and words (EUCLID 21, 56).

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I agree with the terms in the definitions in toto in both references, which clearly expressed the notion of English plain language. Starting from today, I will commit myself to use and practicing plain English language. I also appreciate the EUCLID's effort to impose students to write plain English in their assignments and academic papers. I must expressly acknowledge my awareness of using the simple English language has increased. I will also recommend that the University include a chapter for the Plain English language in the coursepack explaining the notion and principles of the simple English language.

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7) THE SIXTH POINT DISCUSSED: BRITISH ENGLISH

The issue of British English versus American English is not a new phenomenon. This debate has existed since American English was born. The English language is neither my mother tongue nor a primary language around the world where I live. According to the constitution, my official language is Somali, followed by Arabic language (<http://mop.gov.so/wp-content/uploads/2018/04/Somalia-Constitution2012.pdf>).

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It is true the American English is growing and vast, increasing among communities. The reason why the American English spreads over to large territories is due to-among other things- economic, political, and technological advancement (EUCLID 2021,27). Personally, it seems I am familiar with the British English of American English due to my educational background. I used most of my school years in Arabic as a medium of instruction, but there was the English language that I was taking along with other subjects. The English language teachers used British English in terms of spelling and pronunciation. For example, I practiced "colour" instead of "color." Likewise, during my postgraduate study at International Islamic University Malaysia (IIUM), the University used British English because of the British colony and influence.

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I am not against using the American version of English, but I emphasized my personal experience and connection to British English. I believe that British English is the mother of other versions of English.; be they American, Australian, and others as they emerge.

8) LATIN ABBREVIATIONS

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Employing Latin abbreviations is common to academic writing. In my English writing career, I have come across many abbreviated expressions used for scholarly writing, such as, e.g., etc., vs. and *ibid*.

Initially, I had an impression that those terms are English like any other word in the English language until I enrolled research methodology course during my master study. Since then, I have realized that there are Latin expressions. Thus, formal English writing does not allow us to write as we like or think. There are restrictions sometimes on how and what to write in the academic papers, unlike informal writings. For instance, the coursepack advised me not to use contractions (it's) to facilitate easy reading for the reviewer/instructor (EUCLID 2021, 12).

On the other hand, as briefly explained above, writers can use familiar abbreviations in scholarly writings. They may not need to define these abbreviations in the definition sections of their papers. On the contrary, some views are against their use in academic essays (Murphy and Anne, 2009, 16).

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In my view, these abbreviations are applicable for academic purposes because they are short and straightforward, although they are not suitable for all academic papers. The reason is that readers have different levels of knowledge and background to understand such abbreviations quickly and clearly. I will recommend only those abbreviated expressions for high levels of academic writings like EUCLID essential papers.

9) CONCLUSION

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I am confident this course is my first ladder to professional, academic development and success. Before I enrolled in this subject, I had wrong assumptions about my writing skills and knowledge level. Nevertheless, the new exposure I acquired and gained from the course materials, including the video and other recommended sources, have proven that assumption wrong.

The paper explained the principles and steps of essay writing, how to tackle and avoid Plagiarism during writing, taking authors' perspectives and views seriously without patronizing them, and proper use of Turabian style as an approved referencing guide by EUCLID.

The course captured and covered the essential information one could think of when it comes to academic writing. It is an excellent and well-composed material that can easily guide EUCLID students. However, there is always room for improvement. If I am not

wrong, the areas relating to the meaning of the essay and principles of using plan English language require further elaborations in the coursepack, so I would recommend for the authors to consider them by any chance in the future revisions and amendments.

Reference List

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 3rd ed. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui: Euclid University.

Oshima, Alice, and Ann Hogue. 2007. *Introduction to Academic Writing*. Longman: Pearson.

Murphy and Anne. 2009. *General Guide for Academic Writing and Presentation of Written Assignments*. Dublin: Dublin Institute of Technology.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.

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